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Analysis of Errors in the Use of Punctuation Marks and Writing Words on Signboards in the Kayuagung Area

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Abstract

Language is an arbitrary system of sound symbols used by members of a society to cooperate, interact, and identify themselves. The problem in this study is the misuse of punctuation marks and errors in writing words on signboards in the Kayuagung area. This study aims to describe the errors in the use of punctuation marks and word writing errors on signboards in the Kayuagung area in particular. Thus it can provide information, how to use punctuation and write words correctly in accordance with Enhanced Spelling (EYD) so that these mistakes are expected not to be repeated again. The method used in this study is qualitative descriptive method. The data collection technique used in this study is to use observation techniques, documentation, see notes. The object used is a signboard or signpost located in the Kayuagung area. The result of this study is that there are still many errors found in the use of punctuation marks on signage for one's title. Errors in writing words such as errors in the use of standard words, and errors in combining words.

Keyword: Error, Punctuation, Word Writing

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INTRODUCTION

According to KBBI (Big Dictionary Indonesian) edition IV (2014: 16), language is an arbitrary system of sound symbols used by members of a society to cooperate, interact, and identify themselves. According to Koentjaraningrat, 1992 (quoted in detikedu), language is part of culture. Language and culture are interconnected. According to Sapir (1921: 3), language is an instinctive method that humans have to communicate ideas, emotions, and desires, using various symbols made for certain purposes. The main function of language is in the emotional, intellectual, and social development of students.

According to tarigan (quoted in the journal Riri: 2019), language errors are deviations from the determinants of communication and applicable grammatical rules, especially Indonesian. According to Ellis, 1987 (quoted in the journal Putri, 2021), language error analysis is a procedure used by researchers and teachers, which includes collecting samples of student material, recognizing these errors, clarifying them, based on hypothesized causes, and evaluating their seriousness. Meanwhile, according to Supriyani and Ida (2016: 70), language error is the use of a form of speech from various linguistic elements including words, phrases, clauses, and sentences that deviate from predetermined linguistic rules.

Nameplate has a meaning, that is, a board used to notify or inform a company, office or person's name. In addition, signage is usually also used to offer complete goods or services along with addresses. Signage is very helpful for visitors to find the building or place of business they want to go to. The nameplate has two elements, namely visual elements and text elements, where the visual elements in the nameplate or signpost are images, color harmony, thickness and font size. While the text element contained in the signboard is in the form of writing containing information about the identity of the store or the identity of a person. The problem discussed in this study is "Analysis of Error in the Use of Punctuation and Word Writing on Signboards in the Kayuagung Area". Writing errors on signboards are still common in the Kayuagung area. These errors are caused by the influence of the use of everyday language or writing written based on the way people pronounce, ignorance of the General Guidelines for Spelling Indonesian. Therefore, the purpose of this study is to describe the

errors in the use of punctuation marks and word writing errors on signboards in the Kayuagung area in particular. Thus it can provide information, how to use punctuation and write words correctly in accordance with Enhanced Spelling (EYD) so that these mistakes are expected not to be repeated again.

RESEARCH METHODS

The method used in this study is qualitative descriptive method. According to Sukmadinata (2015: 72), descriptive research is the most basic form of research, aimed at describing or describing phenomena that are natural or human engineering. Qualitative method is a method of assessment or research method on a problem that is not carried out using statistical procedures but by explaining. Data analysis techniques with a system of recording, analyzing, and explaining problems related to data in the form of sentences, errors in the use of signs, writing errors and errors in combining words on signboards (plang) in the Kayuagung area.

DISCUSSION

Based on the results of research conducted, in the Kayuagung area there are still many errors found in the use of punctuation, writing words and errors in combining words on the signboard.

1. Apotik

Figure 1

The word "**Apotik**" is a non-standard word according to the General Guidelines for Spelling Indonesian. Because, the correct writing according to the General Spelling Guidelines Indonesian is "**Apotek**". The meaning of pharmacy is a means of health services to help improve health for the community, pharmacy is also a place of practice for pharmacist professionals in doing pharmaceutical work.

2. Praktek

Figure 2

The word "**Praktek**" is a non-standard word according to the General Guidelines for Spelling Indonesian. Because, the correct writing in accordance with the General Spelling Guidelines Indonesian is "**Praktik**". According to the Great Dictionary Indonesian Practice is, the actual implementation of what is mentioned in theory.

3. SYAHRIL AKIP, SH. MH

The writing of the titles "**SH and MH**" is an error in the use of punctuation. Because of the use of double degree name punctuation in a person's name, a person should use a comma (,) after the first degree name. The correct writing is "**Syahrial Akip, S.H., M.H.**".

4. Dr. Rusli Muchtar, Sp. OG

Figure 4

The writing of the title "**Dr. Rusli**" is an error in the use of capital letters. Because the writing of the name of the doctor's degree should use lowercase letters while the use of capital letters in the title "Dr" states that a person has a "Doctorate" degree or someone has completed S.3 education. The correct writing for the medical title is "**dr. Rusli Muchtar, Sp. OG**".

5. Di Jual

Figure 5

The word "**Di Jual**" is an error in writing the word. Where the words "In and Sell" should be combined, because the word is a prefix not a preposition. A prefix is a marker that a passive verb should be written in conjunction with the word that follows it, for example: eaten, drank, sold, read and written. So, the correct writing is "**Dijual**".

6. Lrg Kabul Pasar Kayuagung

Figure 6

In the case as we can see in picture 6 "**Lrg Kabul Pasar Kayuagung**" in plain view there is no error in the writing. However, in the rules for writing abbreviations according to PUEBI the word "Lrg" that does not end with a tili sign (.) is a mistake. Because, if an abbreviation consists of three or more letters, then the abbreviation must be followed by a period (.), for example etc., et al, lrg, etc. so, the correct writing is "**Lrg. Kabul Pasar Kayuagung**".

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the above research, it can be concluded that. Punctuation errors, word usage errors, and errors in combining words on signboards in the Kayuagung area are still widely found. This is caused by habits in the use of everyday language, lack of knowledge about Perfected Spelling in Indonesian, and lack of accuracy from the community which is one of the factors that cause language errors so that people forget the function of spelling, punctuation, the use of capital letters and word choice.

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